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Eustress and Its Enhancing Powers: When Our Mind Is Its Own Psychotropic

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Introduction

Stress, as research suggests, can now be considered an epidemic that has pushed humanity on the verge of a breakdown for over a decade, negatively affecting the mental state and physical health of some groups more than others, such as medical professionals (Newbegin, 2014). However, despite stress becoming more and more prevalent and noticed in the 21st century, an often overlooked fact is that stress can be managed and turned into something beneficial (Craig, 1991). Employers and managers alike have tried to induce positive stress in their workers to achieve developments without having to distress them, and the terminology *eustress* was coined by Hans Selye in 1987 to describe such stress that could have a positive impact on one's performance.

Stress, which was defined by Hans Selye as the general response of the human body towards a demand, has always been a double-edged sword in a way that to some people, stress is a catalyst for disaster, preventing them from functioning effectively, sometimes even taking a toll on their physical health as well (Fink, 2016). For example, according to Fink (2016), job stress is proven to be associated with cardiovascular diseases, addictions, and mental illnesses such as anxiety and depression. On the other hand, the same pressure that can be crippling to some can improve others' immune systems and motivate them to do better in their work at the same time (Fuller, 1983). While people can show a higher and more satisfactory level of performance when faced with higher standards, they can also crumble and experience burnouts when introduced to too much stress. It can be concluded that stress is a very delicate matter to deal with, and it requires careful consideration to use it as a device to induce motivation (Nelson & Simmons, 2003).

Some companies are guilty of assigning their workers with extremely simple tasks which most probably stems from over fixation on division of tasks whereas some companies are guilty of putting too many hats on the same worker or group of workers to reduce the amount of payroll to be paid. Many workers experience weariness towards their jobs due to being assigned overly-easy tasks that are not stimulating, whereas many are overwhelmed by the turbulence of having too many tasks at once. For example, a factory worker who is only tasked to move objects from point A to point B for an infinite amount of times could experience extreme boredom which might lead to negative stress, and a hotel receptionist who is tasked to perform multiple chores at the same time such as greeting guests, receiving and making calls, managing reservations, and inputting data could become overburdened, which might also lead to negative stress (Hargrove, Becker & Hargrove, 2015).

A study done by Folkman and Lazarus in 1985 (as cited in Nelson & Simmons, 2003) involving undergraduate students enrolled in a psychology course found that people can experience different levels of stress caused by the same stressor and that both positive and negative stress can be present at the same time during the same situation because every stress-inducing experience has a level of ambiguity to it. The students' emotional responses before, during, and after their exams were examined, and their perceptions of harm and benefit were measured by their emotions. Other than that, students reported experiencing both distress and eustress during the entire experience because the exams and the act of waiting for the results of the exams were perceived as both a threat and a challenge at the same time. In conclusion, the effects and significance of a stressor is determined by how the experiencer interprets it (Lovallo, 1997).

Supporting Studies

Tieman (2016) conducted a study involving 154 participants of different nationalities and ages ranging from 18 to 55. The participants' distress and eustress traits were measured in order to classify them into two groups: the (high) distress group and the (high) eustress group. From this study, it was found that participants belonging to the distress group suffered from a more elevated level of stress before and after the experiment compared to participants from the eustress group. This means that the idea of the study itself was enough to raise the stress levels of the distress group and long-term stressors have a more significant effect on the distress group even though they can still badly affect the eustress group to an extent (Suedfeld, 1997). In addition, since the same stressor can manifest differently in different people (Selye, 1975), according to Henning, Laschefsi and Opper, the effects of stress can also be felt physiologically in addition to psychologically (as cited in Nelson & Simmons, 2003).

A study conducted by Hoffman-Goetz in 1994 focusing on the association between eustress and tumor metastasis concluded that there is a positive correlation between eustress responses generated by physical exercise and the human body's immune response to limit tumor metastasis. This is due to the fact that physical exercise, which produces eustress responses, can in turn generate more natural killer cells and macrophages in the body. Another study conducted by Parker and Ragsdale in 2015 involving 1,195 full-time day shift employees of various ethnicities, genders, and occupational backgrounds concluded that stress and eustress can have an impact on fatigue levels during work throughout the day. Employees who report a higher level of stress are more fatigued when working compared to ones who report a lower level of stress, and a high rate of energy depletion can in turn cause negative outcomes such as loss of memory, higher risk of accidents, and ineffective information processing.

Intervention

With much evidence showing how eustress can have a significantly positive psychological and physiological impact for people of various demographics, it is imperative for interventions to be conducted to increase eustress and positive outcomes. For example, Sanders (2019) had conducted a randomized intervention trial to change the mindset of university students by increasing their eustress levels. Participants were university students of different genders, sexes, ethnicities, and ages ranging from 18 to 22. The number of participants amounted to 236 people altogether.

As an initial step, participants were randomly assigned to either the control group or the treatment group. Then, each participant's overall initial perceived stress, stress mindset, and demographic are measured using self-report scales and questionnaires. The self-report scale to measure perceived stress consisted of 10 questions and the self-report scale to measure stress mindset consisted of 8 questions, whereas participants' demographic was measured using a specially designed questionnaire. This was to make sure that the results or final outcomes of the intervention can be compared to the initial measurements.

The intervention was conducted by screening two online short videos every session with a runtime of approximately 3 minutes per video. There were 3 sessions in total over the span of 10 weeks. The treatment group was shown videos about improving stress mindset that were previously used in a similar experiment, whereas the control group was shown videos about astronomy. Both videos were factual. At the end of the intervention, all participants were asked to complete a post-intervention survey to measure the treatment effects. This overall method was chosen because it required very minimum materials, expense, effort, and time to affect a large number of individuals (Sanders, 2019).

After the post-intervention survey was completed and analyzed using the SPSS software, the results of the intervention show that there was a significant difference in

mindset for the treatment group (Crum, Savoley & Achor, 2013). The treatment group had developed a better mindset regarding stress, in which they think stress can have a more positive impact on their daily lives. The mean stress mindset score had gone from 1.76 (.58) in week 1 to an average score of 2.33 (.55) in week 10. In addition, treatment group participants had also scored .55 higher compared to the control group participants.

However, even though there was a significant change in stress mindset, there was no significant difference in overall perceived stress for both the treatment and control group. The newly-acquired positive mindset still needed time to develop and manifest into the participants' overall perceived stress levels (Cohen, Kamarck & Mermelstein, 1983; Park et al., 2018). Other than that, because the initial number of participants was considerably large, there were many individuals who were unable to complete the intervention from the beginning until the end. Some were unable to attend some of the sessions, whereas some simply did not come back to complete the post-treatment survey. In addition, the data collected in the intervention was self-reported by filling in surveys and questionnaires, which can be considered biased and can be easily manipulated by the participants. Lastly, since the intervention was carried out digitally via online videos, there was no guarantee that participants paid full attention to all the videos without skipping any parts or letting the video run in the background while they performed some other task(s), which in turn would make the results less accurate or conclusive.

Future Directions

While the number of studies and trials regarding positive stress and positive stress mindsets has greatly increased in the 21st century, researchers can still offer many contributions and provide answers regarding areas that have yet to be studied and explored thoroughly. Researchers could develop and experiment with newer and more comprehensive

methods of coping with stress and developing better stress mindsets (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Other than finding new methods, researchers could also conduct more research on the effectiveness and efficiency of these methods to ensure success and provide a deeper insight on the field of positive stress and stress mindsets by testing these methods on a wider range of sample populations (involving individuals from various demographics such as age, ethnicity, gender, sex, educational background, occupational background, etc.).

Conclusion

In conclusion, when supported by a positive and constructive mindset, stress can be something motivating and encouraging, and this kind of positive stress is called eustress, as coined by Hans Selye. Moreover, eustress can not only have a significantly positive psychological impact but also physiologically. Eustress has been proven by research to have the ability to prevent and decelerate the development of physiological ailments such as tumors and heart attacks, and psychological symptoms such as work stress and anxiety. In addition, interventions can be done to acquire the mindset needed to be able to convert psychological pressure into positive stress despite their limitations. In turn, with time, the overall quality of life and perceived stress levels of individuals who come across these stresses can be positively impacted or improved, even if the type or source of stressors differs from one another. Lastly, as proven by the randomized trial conducted by Sanders in 2019, video-based intervention methods are also effective for the general public since the results of said study showed how many people of different demographics and backgrounds reacted similarly to the intervention, which also shows how the effects and significance of eustress are universally experienced.

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